

Girls Outdoors

Longitudinal Study:

Methods Technical Report

Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1)
Work Package 2

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1. Introduction

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the approach for the longitudinal Girls Outdoors Study. The study forms part of the *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* (JHI-C6-1) research project funded by the Scottish Government's Rural and Environmental Sciences & Analytical Services (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme (SRP) 2022-27.

An overarching and longstanding interest of the Scottish Government is in increasing use of outdoor spaces (green and blue). Encouraging, managing, and investing in this behaviour has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to planning, environment, public health, tourism, and education. As such, recreational use is a vital consideration in land management decisions, with important environmental implications tied to *how* people engage with nature. For example, while increased engagement with the outdoors during the COVID-19 pandemic was widely welcomed (Armstrong et al., 2021), there was an unfortunate rise in undesirable behaviour (e.g. leaving litter, lighting fires in sensitive areas; see [Irresponsible Camping in National Park](#)).

The aim for the *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* project is to investigate possibilities and constraints for building capacities for reciprocal nature engagement through aspects of environmental settings (type, quality), users (barriers, behaviours), mechanisms for benefit (green prescribing, outdoor learning), and investment (costs, preventative spend). Our use of the language 'reciprocal nature engagement' reflects a move toward a less utilitarian framing of the people-nature connection than might be suggested in phrases such as 'use of the outdoors' (see Irvine, Brown & Thompson, 2024 for overview). The overall project addresses the increasingly recognised need to foster conditions that support a reciprocal relationship between people and the environment - one that nurtures human communities while encouraging active care for the natural world.

1.1 Rationale for the Girls Outdoors Study

Spending time outdoors in natural environments during childhood positively affects adult wellbeing, nature connection, frequency of engagement with the outdoors, and environmental stewardship behaviours (e.g. Wells & Lekies, 2006; Ward-Thompson, Aspinall, & Montarino, 2008). Recent reviews highlight the positive and wide-ranging impact of outdoor learning/education on children and young people (age 3-18 years old), including academic outcomes, health and wellbeing, interpersonal and social, confidence, skill, building, and behavioural (Christie & Higgins, 2020; MacLean et al., 2023).

The frequency of nature contact may, however, shape the extent to which natural environments deliver benefits to marginalised population subgroups (Colley, Irvine & Currie, 2022). Compared to adults, young people are less likely to spend time outdoors (Oppliger et al., 2019) with a widely acknowledged 'teenage dip' in young people's engagement in outdoor activities, especially in the early teenage years (Richardson et al., 2019). Additionally, there is a recognised 'gender gap' in engagement with the outdoors (Dobson et al., 2019). Parks and recreational areas are used differently – and generally less often – by girls than boys (Evenson et al., 2016) and over time, females' experience of, and engagement with, the outdoors changes.

Young girls are thus an important population groups that are known to participate in outdoor recreation less frequently. The Girls Outdoors Study specifically seeks to shed insight on the experience of pre-teen/teenage girls in different types of outdoor settings. It utilises a life course perspective which considers the temporal context of behaviour, viewing behaviour from a developmental standpoint, where focus is placed on an individual's unfolding sequence of roles and experiences throughout life and the transition points that mark changes in these roles or states across the study (Elder et al., 2003). Using a life course lens enables us to understand the points at which, and why, this group (dis)engages with the outdoors, their behaviours in, and their relationship with the outdoors. This study thus provides in-depth insight and a voice from a group who are seldom the focus of nature-engagement research.

Insight can inform the design, management, improvement of, and investment in places and spaces that support nature engagement by – and its benefits for – this underrepresented group. More widely, the insight could support development of initiatives to promote outdoor recreation amongst young females, including consideration for design of and training for outdoor learning/ outdoor education programmes, policy, and investment as a mechanism to facilitate nature engagement.

1.2 Aims and objectives of the technical report

The purpose of this technical report is to detail the research processes within the Girls Outdoors (GO) Study. In addition to describing the design for, sampling and participants recruited to the study, we explain the choice and implementation of methods used in and planned for the three waves of data collection: Wave 1 completed 2024; Waves 2 and 3 scheduled for 2025 and 2026, respectively. By outlining our approach in detail, one objective is to enable the reader to gain a clear understanding of the specific steps, procedures, methods, and considerations that inform this study.

Beyond serving as a guide for the project's execution, a second objective is for the report to act as a reflective document during and after implementation. By documenting our planned research process, we can reflect on and invite feedback (e.g. about relevant studies, methods, recently published reports, emerging policy direction) to facilitate continued relevance. Undertaking an ongoing and retrospective assessment of our methods and processes will help to evaluate how effectively our approaches worked in practice, providing the research team, other researchers, and relevant stakeholders with insights to inform future policy, practice, and research.

2. Research design

This section outlines the aims and objectives of the GO study and presents a framework for its implementation over the years 2023–2027. It details the study's structure, including the methods and research questions. Furthermore, it introduces the thematic focus areas and methodological adaptations designed to provide a nuanced understanding of the factors shaping participants' relationships with the outdoors.

2.1 Aims and objectives

The GO study is a longitudinal case study employing a mix of methods to gain in-depth insights into the experiences of pre-teen to teenage girls in a large urban area. The study aims to explore

the personal, lived experiences of these girls' (non)engagement with the outdoors. Its specific objectives are to:

1. Explore, understand, and document young females' (non)engagement with the outdoors leading up to and during their pre-teen to teenage years.
2. Identify factors, such as the quality of outdoor spaces, that influence their (dis)engagement.
3. Provide insights to inform policy and practice on the provision and accessibility of safe outdoor spaces for this demographic.

This in-depth field-investigation will pay particular attention to: (i) personal experience of outdoor space and recreational patterns; (ii) the temporal relationship with and benefits derived from nature; (iii) perceived quality of outdoor; (iv) nature engagement capabilities and care for nature; and (v) identifying the moments of change in life that affect increased/decreased engagement with nature.

To achieve our objectives, we have structured the 4-year longitudinal study (2023–2027) into three waves (Table 1). The study employs a developmental design, where methods for Wave 2 are refined based on findings from Wave 1, and methods for Wave 3 are further refined using insights from both Waves 1 and 2. This adaptive approach builds in flexibility, allowing methods and research questions to be adjusted as needed to stay effective and relevant.

Each wave comprises six key phases:

1. **Refining Study Design:** While the overarching study design was established at the outset in consultation with the JHI-C6-1 Steering Group, each wave begins with a detailed review of research questions, how and what data will be collected, how it will be analysed, and the specific outcomes we aim to achieve.
2. **Ethical Reviews:** Addressing ethical considerations and preparing applications for review by the James Hutton Institute's Research Ethics Committee, RESAS, and the respective local council.
3. **Preparation for Data Collection:** This includes participant recruitment, planning, and preparing materials and equipment.
4. **Data Collection:** Conducting the planned field-based data collection activities.
5. **Data Analysis:** Analysing the collected data to draw insights.
6. **Writing and Reporting:** Writing up findings, preparing reports and briefs, presenting at relevant conferences, and developing manuscripts in preparation for academic publications.

As detailed in Sections 2.2 and 2.3, to allow for longitudinal comparison the study employs a consistent set of methods and core set of research questions across all waves. Each wave also incorporates wave-specific methods tailored to focus on a specific theme, resulting in distinct research questions for each wave (outlined in Table 1). The variation in research questions is intentional and reflects both the **longitudinal nature of the study** and the **different thematic focus of each wave**.

Each wave is designed to explore specific aspects of outdoor engagement that align with participants' experiences over time:

- **Wave 1** establishes a **baseline** by investigating **patterns of engagement and disengagement with the outdoors from early childhood to the present** (when interviews took place for Wave 1). This phase focuses on understanding initial experiences, key life events, and enablers/barriers influencing outdoor engagement.
- **Wave 2** continues the timeline from Wave 1, focussing on the **changes in outdoor engagement since Wave 1**, particularly following the **transition to secondary school**. The thematic emphasis of Wave 2 is an exploration of the **key qualities of outdoor spaces valued by this age group**, providing deeper insight into their evolving perceptions and preferences, which emerged in Wave 1.
- **Wave 3** re-asks the set of questions from Wave 1 and continues to track **shifts in outdoor engagement since Wave 2**. The thematic focus of Wave 3 will be **on nature engagement capabilities and fostering respect for nature**. This wave builds on previous insights while delving into an exploration of participants' developing sense of respect for nature and confidence in engaging with outdoor spaces.

In summary, while some **core research questions** remain consistent across Waves 1 and 3 to allow for **longitudinal comparisons**, each wave also introduces **wave-specific questions** that align with the study's thematic focus and objectives. This ensures that we are not only tracking changes over time but also capturing new and relevant aspects of outdoor engagement as participants grow and their relationships with outdoor spaces evolve.

Table 1: Timeline, Methods, and Research Questions for each Wave of the Girls Outdoors (GO) Longitudinal Study (2023-2027)

GO: Longitudinal study timeline			
Wave	Start and end	Methods	Research Questions
1	November 2023 – March 2024 Participants are in Primary 7 (P7)	Structured interview (survey) Semi-structured interview (‘River of Life’ method)	1) What are recent use patterns of different types of outdoor spaces amongst the participants? 2) How do the participants perceive nature and reflect on their connection to it and their interest in caring for it? 3) How do the participants perceive their capabilities and experiences related to engaging with outdoor spaces? 4) What key life events and transitions relate to participants' engagement with outdoor spaces? 5) What are the participants' experiences of different outdoor spaces and activities? 6) What enablers and barriers impact participants' engagement with outdoor spaces, and how have these evolved across the study?

2	April – June 2025	Semi-structured interview (‘River of Life’ method)	1) How do transitions and changes since starting secondary school relate to participants’ (dis)engagement with outdoor spaces? 2) What do the participants consider to be the qualities of good outdoor spaces?
	Participants are in Secondary 1 (S1)	Photovoice technique	3) How do certain characteristics of outdoor spaces influence the perceptions, experiences, and interactions with outdoor spaces amongst the participants?
3	April – June 2026	Structured interview (survey)	1) What are recent use patterns of different types of outdoor spaces amongst the participants? 2) How do the participants perceive nature and reflect on their connection to it and their interest in caring for it? 3) How do the participants perceive their capabilities and experiences related to engaging with outdoor spaces?
	Participants are in Secondary 2 (S2)	Semi-structured interview (‘River of Life’ method)	4) What factors influence the participants’ engagement with and preferences for outdoor spaces since S1? 5) What are the participants capabilities for engaging with (unfamiliar) outdoor spaces and to what extent can a VTN enhance their comfort and confidence?
		Virtual Tour of Nature (VTN)	6) How do the participants view their role in caring for nature, and to what extent can a VTN inspire their interest and willingness to care?

2.2 Longitudinal timeline

The study will follow a cohort of girls aged 10/11 (Primary 7) in Wave 1, through their transition to secondary school in Wave 2 at age 11-12(13) (Secondary 1), and into their teenage years at age 12-13(14) (Secondary 2) in Wave 3.

Tracking changes between the Wave 1, 2 and 3

- Structured Interview (Survey):** In Wave 1 and 3, we will use the same structured interview (survey) questions to establish a ‘baseline’ (Wave 1) and identify any changes (Wave 3) in relation to participants’ frequency of visits to different types of outdoor spaces, their relationship with and connection to nature, and nature engagement capabilities, capturing shifts as participants move from pre-teen years to adolescence.

- **Visual Timeline ('River of Life' Method):** We will incorporate a subset of the semi-structured interview questions ('longitudinal questions') from Wave 1 across all waves to monitor ongoing changes in participants' (dis)engagement with outdoor spaces. These changes will be visualised using an adapted 'River of Life' method (as further explained in Section 2.3), creating a continuous timeline. In Wave 1, the focus will be on developing this timeline by mapping outdoor activities and experiences alongside corresponding key life events, from early childhood to the present (point at which Wave 1 interviews took place). This will explore both regular activities (e.g. cycling to school) and one-off experiences (e.g. a school trip to an outdoor centre). Waves 2 and 3 will build on this timeline by revisiting the 'longitudinal questions' to track changes across the study, exploring outdoor activities throughout the week, weekends, and holidays, including those with family, extended family, friends, school, and clubs.

Using consistent methods and collecting the same types of data in Waves 1, 2, and 3 from the same cohort of girls will be essential for identifying these changes and will reduce the reliance on participants' recall at the end of the study (Ployhart & Vandenberg, 2010). Although Waves 2 and 3 will additionally employ different participatory visual methods, these still explore similar themes, enabling the study to track when and how changes occur, whether gradually, in bursts, or with periods of stability (Singer & Willett, 2003). The following section presents an overview of all the methods employed in this study.

Key thematic area of exploration per Wave

In addition to updating the visual timeline at the start of each wave of data collection, each wave will also explore a specific key theme in greater depth.

- **Wave 1: Key Moments of (dis)Engagement with the Outdoors since Childhood:** Establishing a baseline by investigating patterns of engagement and disengagement with the outdoors from early childhood to the present (winter 2023/2024).
- **Wave 2: Outdoor space Qualities:** This wave explores the key qualities of outdoor spaces valued by this age group, including factors that enhance or hinder their use and enjoyment of outdoor spaces.
- **Wave 3: Nature Engagement Capabilities and Respect for Nature:** Examining how participants' connection with nature has evolved since Wave 1, with a focus on their confidence in engaging with outdoor spaces, their perceived capabilities in navigating and appreciating nature, and their attitudes towards environmental stewardship ('respect for nature').

2.3 Key methods

The Girls Outdoors Study adopts a mixed methods approach to explore the diverse experiences of a cohort of girls with outdoor spaces, following them from P7 to S2. The key methods include structured and semi-structured interviews, along with visual methods to gain comprehensive insights into participants' lived experience with different types of outdoor spaces. By using a developmental and life course perspective, the study is designed to track changes in their (dis)engagement with the outdoors across the study and explore the factors that influence this. Outlined below are the key details of each method used in this study across the three waves. Further information on each method is provided in Sections 7–9.

- **Structured interviews (survey):** In Waves 1 and 3, structured interviews (survey) will follow a survey format. These include closed-ended questions to assess participants' frequency of visits to different types of outdoor spaces, modes of travel, their relationship with and connection to nature, and nature engagement capabilities. Follow-up questions further explore the reasons behind participants' responses, providing deeper insights into their nature engagement and experiences.
- **Semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method):** Using a life course perspective, we conduct semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method) by asking participants about their outdoor activities from childhood to the present, using an adapted 'River of Life' method (a visual timeline activity based on Colley, Currie, et al. (2022), where participants visually map key life events (e.g. house moves, school changes, new friendships) and outdoor activities along a timeline. This timeline helps to identify patterns of increased or decreased outdoor engagement, potentially linked to these key life events. The same set of questions will be asked across all waves to track changes in participants' outdoor engagement over the course of the study.
- **Visual methods:** (i) In Waves 1, 2, and 3, we co-create a visual timeline with participants that tracks their outdoor engagements from early childhood through to Wave 3 in 2026. (ii) In Wave 2, we will incorporate the photovoice technique, asking participants to photograph outdoor spaces they use to explore their perceptions of outdoor space quality; this links the GO study (Work Package 2) with the Investing in Green/blue Space strand (Work Package 1) within the wider *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* project. (iii) In Wave 3, participants will take part in a Virtual Tour of Nature, designed as part of the wider project's Nature-Engagement Capabilities for Reciprocal Care strand (Work Package 3), which explores different outdoor settings (park, beach, wooded area) and will be used to discuss nature capabilities and respectful behaviours in these environments ('care for nature'); this integrates Work Packages 2 and 3.

This mixed methods approach will enable a comprehensive understanding of how girls engage with outdoor spaces, whether through formal (e.g. school trips) or informal (e.g. family outings) mechanisms, or solitary experiences. By using a variety of methods, the study addresses the research questions from multiple angles, capturing richer and more nuanced insights into participants' outdoor engagement. In addition, offering diverse ways for participants to share their experiences - through both semi-structured and structured conversations, as well as visual and creative methods - ensures inclusivity. This approach accommodates different neurotypes and communication preferences, providing every participant with an accessible and engaging way to contribute.

3. Reciprocal research

The GO study is underpinned by a reciprocal research approach, which seeks to create a mutually beneficial experience for both the participants and the research team. This approach goes beyond traditional, extractive research models that can lead to research fatigue by emphasising ethical engagement, participant empowerment, and sustained involvement (Clark, 2008). Reciprocal research offers two key advantages: first, it addresses ethical concerns by ensuring that participants are not merely subjects but active contributors within the research process; second, it facilitates richer, more meaningful engagement, which ultimately improves both recruitment, continued participation, and the quality of the data collected.

At its core, reciprocal research is grounded in the idea that participants should not only provide data but also benefit from the research process. This approach aligns with ethical commitments to mutual benefit and respect, fostering an environment where participants feel valued, heard, and actively engaged. By creating opportunities for participants to interact more deeply with both the research setting and the process itself, this approach opens doors to rich learning experiences and enhances participants' understanding of the impact of their contributions.

To support this reciprocal engagement, the research team aims to keep participants informed and involved at various stages of the study. Participants are encouraged to ask questions, understand the importance of their role, and see how their input shapes research outcomes. By implementing these practices, the team addresses common issues of disengagement, especially in longitudinal studies and younger populations, such as pre-teen and teenage girls. Research with emerging adult populations often encounters recruitment and retention challenges. However, by embedding reciprocal principles into the study design (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019), the GO study seeks to counter these challenges, fostering sustained engagement and commitment amongst participants.

3.1. Reciprocal elements in the Girls Outdoors Study

Recognising the challenges of retaining younger participants in longitudinal studies, the study focuses on giving back, empowering participants, and supporting personal growth. This section outlines strategies for keeping participants involved, providing valuable experiences, and expressing gratitude, ensuring participants feel valued and invested in the research process. We believe that this approach will encourage them to return and contribute to making their involvement in the study both positive and memorable.

Personal and Professional Growth

In Wave 1, participants and their parents/ carers were invited to the James Hutton Institute for an immersive experience, where they were offered a tour of various departments, explored different research settings, visited laboratories, and engaged with staff from multiple fields. This provided the participants and their parents/ carers with valuable insights into research environments and potential careers, offering a learning opportunity beyond data collection, and offering them a unique opportunity to learn about careers in science. This approach was designed to foster both meaningful engagement and personal investment in the research process.

Retention Activities and 'Giving Back'

Retention is a key challenge in any longitudinal study. As part of our retention strategy, we are keeping participants engaged by sending personal cards and newsletters with updates, including visuals such as photos of the research team analysing data. Similar engaging activities are planned for future waves to ensure the experience remains enriching and rewarding for the participants. These activities aim to demystify the research process for the participants and may inspire future career interests, fostering professional growth even at this early stage of their lives.

Material Gratitude

At the most basic level, the study will ensure that participants are materially thanked for their time and effort. Participants will be reimbursed for any costs incurred, such as travel expenses, and they receive small thank-you gifts as a gesture of appreciation in each Wave. In addition, age-

appropriate refreshments will be provided during interviews to enhance their overall experience and make participation more enjoyable.

3.2. Enhancing data quality through reciprocity

In addition to the ethical benefits, employing reciprocal research is expected to enhance the quality of the data collected. By building trust and fostering deeper connections with participants, the research team anticipates more honest, reflective, and rich data. Participants are more likely to open up and provide detailed insights into their lived experiences when they feel valued and engaged in the process. This is particularly important in a study like GO, which seeks to understand personal and sometimes sensitive experiences of (non)engagement with outdoor spaces.

By maintaining a reciprocal relationship throughout the duration of the study, the research team is better positioned to address the challenges of participant retention and data quality that are often encountered in longitudinal research. This reciprocal model not only enhances the study's ethical integrity but also ensures that participants gain personal value from their involvement, while contributing more meaningfully to the research process.

4. Population and sampling

We recruited pre-teenage girls in their final year of primary school (P7, aged 10/11-12) from a large urban area (our case study area). The aim is to follow this cohort through a key transition in their life course - from primary to secondary school - tracking changes in outdoor engagement until they reach S2 (aged 12-13(14)). This period represents a critical developmental shift often associated with changes in behaviours, with the study exploring how these changes relate to their engagement with outdoor spaces.

Participants were recruited primarily through schools in a large urban area; the location was selected based on practical considerations. The decision to recruit through schools, rather than community groups or clubs, was made to avoid potential demographic bias and maximise diversity within the sample. Although an initial plan was to include both urban and rural schools, this was revised due to challenges in rural recruitment, travel costs, and logistical feasibility. Ultimately, the focus on an urban setting allowed for a more manageable study and provided the opportunity to closely examine changes across the study within a particular subset of the population.

Recruitment efforts focused on ensuring a diverse sample by targeting schools with varying levels of ethnic, economic, and environmental diversity. This was assessed using factors such as pupil ethnic background, free school meal data (as a proxy for socioeconomic status), and access to outdoor spaces in their local environments. To identify suitable schools, an initial shortlist was created based on diversity rankings. However, due to limited responses from the shortlisted schools, outreach was extended to all schools in the top 20 longlist. When this still resulted in insufficient participation, we further expanded recruitment beyond the original list and included guide clubs to increase representation. Ultimately, we successfully established contact with 12 schools, both within and beyond the top 20, achieving a broad geographic spread across the urban area.

Participants were invited to express interest through various channels, including returning forms via email, text, or phone. A project mobile phone was used to facilitate communication. Our initial

goal was to recruit 35 girls; we successfully enrolled 24, with 23 recruited through schools and one through a guide's club. Upon reflection, this sample size was deemed sufficient for addressing the study's objectives.

4.1. Research with pre-teen and teenage girls

This section outlines the key considerations and strategies employed in working with this specific demographic, including ethical safeguards, recruitment processes, and methods for building trust and ensuring ongoing participation. By prioritising the wellbeing of the participants and adapting methods to suit their needs, the study aims to create a research environment that is both ethical and effective in capturing the lived experiences of pre-teen to teenage girls in relation to their outdoor engagement. The research design was mindful of the need to reduce the risk of peer pressure effects during the interviews, which is why data collection was conducted on an individual basis. Additionally, data collection was scheduled outside of school or club activities, ensuring that participants were comfortable and able to engage freely without external pressures.

4.1.1. Ethical considerations

Ethical review was undertaken by the James Hutton Institute's Research Ethics Committee, as well as RESAS and the local authority. The study employed layers of consent to ensure that participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, their role, and their right to withdraw at any time. Participants were given clear, age-appropriate information, and the parents/ carers were also informed in detail about the nature of the research. Written consent was secured from both participants and their parents/ carers.

Due to the sensitive nature of working with young participants, a parent/ carer was always present during interviews in Wave 1. In addition, two researchers carried out the interviews together to ensure a safe and supportive environment. We will continue the two-researcher practice in Waves 2 and 3, as it safeguards participants by providing an additional responsible adult to oversee interactions, enhancing accountability in the research process. Moreover, researchers were trained to handle sensitive disclosures, such as instances where participants might reveal illegal activities or other concerning behaviours, such as self-harm or harm to others. If such disclosures occurred, researchers were prepared to follow protocols for safeguarding the participants while maintaining their trust and confidentiality to the extent possible within ethical guidelines. All researchers involved in the study were PVG-checked through the Scottish Protecting Vulnerable Groups (PVG) scheme.

4.1.2. Engaging pre-teen girls in research

Engaging P7 girls in the study involved navigating multiple layers of access through gatekeepers, including the Scottish Government, the local authority, head teachers, class teachers, and parents/ carers. The recruitment process was iterative and reflective, requiring ongoing adjustments based on feedback and logistical challenges. This approach required negotiating access through school administrations and adapting our recruitment strategies based on school priorities and constraints.

We worked closely with gatekeepers within the schools (e.g. head teachers) to tailor to the needs of each school. This included offering 'My World of Work' sessions, where we visited schools to give interactive sessions to classes about research at the James Hutton Institute and STEM opportunities for girls and women. Some schools also advertised the study through bulletins and

newsletters. Although resource-intensive, these efforts successfully built strong relationships with schools, supporting future collaboration - a secondary goal of the recruitment process.

After overcoming the initial hurdle of recruitment by establishing contact with schools, delivering engaging sessions, and explaining the research process to both pupils and staff, we then had to engage with parents/ carers who reached out after their child expressed interest in participating following our school visits. This involved providing a detailed explanation of the research process, being readily available to answer any questions, and building rapport and trust. Establishing this relationship was essential for encouraging their willingness to meet the research team and participate in the study. Throughout, we were careful to emphasise that participation was entirely voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time.

4.1.3. Reflexivity in working with pre-teen and teenage girls

Throughout the recruitment and data collection processes, reflexivity is crucial. Within this project, researchers have been and are engaged in an ongoing dialogue and reflection process around ensuring responsiveness to the needs and concerns of the girls in the study. This includes being mindful of the power dynamics inherent in adult-child interactions and ensuring that the research methods were appropriate for the participants' developmental stage. Reflexivity also extended to how the researchers presented themselves, using language and materials that were accessible and engaging to the age group, and continuously adapting based on the participants' feedback. By adopting a participant-centred approach and being responsive to the unique needs of this demographic, the study aims to ensure ethical integrity and participant wellbeing while successfully gathering valuable data.

5. Analysis

While using a mix of methods across the three waves, the GO study primarily employs qualitative analysis. Data from the survey used in the structured interviews (survey) and the visual data from the photovoice technique will also be predominantly analysed qualitatively, with basic descriptive statistics applied where relevant. This section provides an overview of the analytical approaches: Section 5.1 focuses on the qualitative analysis, Section 5.2 details the application of basic descriptive statistics, Section 5.3 outlines the visual data analysis process, and Section 5.4 explains the data integration process from the multiple methods. This integrated approach facilitates comprehensive methods triangulation, allowing findings to be validated through cross-checking results from different methods to ensure consistency and reliability.

5.1. Qualitative data analysis

All interviews are audio-recorded and transcribed by trusted transcribers who have undertaken a personal disclosure (PVG) check. The transcripts are then quality-checked by the research team before they are uploaded to NVivo software, which aids in organising and coding large datasets. We will employ Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2021).

Central to RTA is its emphasis on reflexivity, where the researchers' own positionality and experiences (e.g. socio-demographic background, their own engagement with nature) are acknowledged as part of the interpretive process. As researchers engage deeply with the data, they will reflect on how their own assumptions and biases might shape the analysis. This iterative approach allows for continuous re-evaluation, moving back and forth between coding and theme development, resulting in more nuanced insights into the participants' experiences. This

approach thus embraces researcher subjectivity, reflexivity, and creativity as essential components of the analytical process, aligning well with the study's focus on understanding the personal, lived experiences of pre-teen to teenage girls in relation to their engagement with the outdoors.

The research team will implement researcher reflexivity through the following approaches:

- Engage in ongoing reflection to recognise and minimise potential biases.
- Use independent coding verification, where multiple researchers review and cross-check data interpretations to ensure consistency.
- Document decisions in the coding and analysis process to enhance transparency and replicability.

Reflexivity requires researchers to be critically aware of their own perspectives, assumptions, and positionality in relation to the study. To systematically integrate reflexivity throughout the research process, the team will implement the above in the following ways:

Ongoing Reflexive Practice

Throughout the study, researchers will engage in continuous self-reflection to identify and mitigate potential biases that could shape data collection, analysis, and interpretation. This will be facilitated through:

- **Reflexive Journaling:** Each researcher will maintain a reflexive journal to document personal thoughts, reactions, and assumptions during data coding and analysis. This will help researchers recognise how their perspectives may influence their interpretation of participants' narratives and adjust their approach accordingly.
- **Reflexive Team Discussions:** Regular team meetings will include structured discussions on reflexivity, where researchers will critically assess their own perspectives and challenge each other's assumptions to ensure balanced and fair interpretations of the data.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** As mentioned above, the research team consists of members from different academic backgrounds. This diversity allows for a range of perspectives in interpreting findings, preventing a single dominant viewpoint from shaping the analysis.

Independent Coding Verification

To enhance reliability and reduce individual researcher bias in the coding process, independent coding verification will be implemented as follows:

- **Multiple Coders:** At least two researchers will code the same subset of interview transcripts independently before comparing and discussing their coding choices. Any discrepancies will be examined and resolved through discussion to reach a consensus, ensuring that the coding scheme remains consistent across all data.
- **Codebook Refinement:** The coding framework will evolve iteratively, with researchers refining definitions and categories based on their reflections and discussions. This will be documented to maintain consistency and transparency in the coding process.
- **Blind Coding Comparison:** In some cases, an additional researcher unfamiliar with the original coding decisions will review the data and provide an independent interpretation. This serves as an additional check to identify potential biases in initial coding decisions.

Documenting Decision-Making for Transparency and Replicability

To ensure that analytical decisions are transparent and replicable, the research team will:

- **Maintain an Audit Trail:** All key decisions made during data analysis—including coding changes, emergent themes, and rationale for interpretative choices—will be recorded in a shared document. This will provide a clear record of how the findings were developed and allow reviewers to follow the analytical process step by step.
- **Thematic Development Logs:** A dedicated log will be maintained to document how themes emerge from the data, noting any shifts in interpretation and the reasons behind them. This will help ensure that themes are derived from the data rather than imposed by researcher expectations.

By combining reflexivity, interdisciplinary collaboration, and systematic triangulation, we strengthen the trustworthiness of our interpretations and ensure that our conclusions provide a balanced and comprehensive reflection of pre-teen girls' evolving engagement with outdoor spaces.

The analysis process will involve four key phases:

1. **Familiarisation with the data:** The first step will involve an in-depth review of the transcribed interviews and visual timelines, immersing the researchers in the data to identify initial patterns and insights.
2. **Coding the data:** We will systematically code the data in NVivo using a researcher-developed set of codes drawn from interview and survey questions. Example codes include key life events, outdoor experiences, and other relevant factors that influence outdoor engagement. New codes will be added to the coding structure should they emerge through the analysis process.
3. **Theme identification:** Themes will be identified through an iterative emergent process. While themes will be anticipated (e.g. informed by our theoretical framework and prior knowledge), they will not be predefined but rather will emerge organically as the researchers engage with the data. Examples of anticipated themes include shifts in outdoor behaviour after transitioning to secondary school, key factors influencing outdoor (dis)engagement. The theme identification process follows a three-step process:
 - a. **Searching for themes:** As coding progresses, we will begin grouping related codes into broader themes that reflect the emerging patterns across the data.
 - b. **Reviewing themes:** These initial themes will be reviewed and refined through an iterative process, with continuous reflection on how they connect to the overall research questions and objectives.
 - c. **Defining and naming themes:** Once a set of stable themes are identified, we will define and clearly name each theme, ensuring that they capture the essence of the participants' experiences as reflected by the codes that make up each theme.
4. **Synthesis:** The final phase will involve synthesising the findings into a coherent narrative, integrating the themes with the broader research aim and objectives to offer a rich interpretation of the girls' outdoor engagement.

5.2. Quantitative data analysis

The structured interviews (survey) involve completing a questionnaire administered through Qualtrics, an online survey platform, generating quantitative data from closed-ended questions,

predominantly Likert scales (a 5-point scale of response options). While the sample size is statistically non-significant, these data will be analysed using basic descriptive statistical techniques, including frequencies, percentages, ranges, and the identification of outliers. This analysis will summarise the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants and their responses, providing an overview of patterns in outdoor behaviour and their relationship with nature across the sample. Examples of such patterns include the frequency of visits to various outdoor settings, the range of nature connection, and participants' nature engagement capabilities.

These quantitative findings serve as a foundational overview, offering a snapshot of patterns within the sample. By asking the same set of questions in Wave 3, we gain insight into changes over time, allowing for a deeper understanding of changes within the sample. These data will be analysed in parallel with the structured interview transcripts, which will undergo qualitative coding using NVivo, as described earlier. By integrating the quantitative data with qualitative insights, we can explore the motivations, attitudes, and contextual factors underlying participants' responses to the closed-ended questions. This approach allows for a richer and more nuanced understanding of outdoor behaviours and connections to nature, balancing numerical patterns with the depth of participants' lived experiences.

5.3. Visual data analysis

Data from the visual methods - including the River of Life timeline that forms part of the semi-structured interview ('River of Life' method) (Waves 1, 2 and 3), the photovoice technique in Wave 2, and the Virtual Tour of Nature in Wave 3 - will be analysed alongside the interview data to deepen our understanding of participants' perceptions and experiences with outdoor spaces. The visual methods will be used to enrich the findings from the interviews, offering additional layers of interpretation and helping to identify any shifts in how participants engage with and perceive outdoor spaces. Details on the analysis of data from these visual methods are provided in the sections describing each data collection wave (Sections 7–9).

5.4. Methods triangulation

The integration of qualitative, quantitative, and visual data offers a comprehensive understanding of the girls' experiences with different types of outdoor spaces between the ages of 10/11 and 13/14. Qualitative analysis from the semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method), along with follow-up questions from the structured interviews (survey), provides in-depth insights into the personal and social factors influencing (dis)engagement with the outdoors. Quantitative data from the closed-ended questions adds perspective on patterns across the study, while the visual methods enrich these findings by incorporating spatial, aesthetic, and experiential dimensions.

By triangulating the findings from the multiple methods, the study generates a holistic view of how participants' engagement with outdoor spaces changes across the study. This approach will ensure a well-rounded interpretation of the study's findings, directly informing the objectives to understand (dis)engagement with the outdoors and providing insights for policy and practice regarding the provision and accessibility of outdoor spaces for this demographic.

6. Limitations and strengths

As with any research, this study will have limitations which we outline here in broad terms, alongside strengths of the approach. In Section 7-9, we provide further and more detailed reflection on these as pertains to each wave. Here we touch on implications of the case study

design, participant sample, and considerations of transferability. Overall, while the case study design and small sample size limit generalisability of the findings, the rich, in-depth data collected across the study will provide valuable insights into the experiences of this specific cohort of girls. The study's findings may offer transferable lessons for similar urban settings and contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing outdoor engagement amongst pre-teen and teenage girls.

6.1. Case study design

Findings will be derived from a mixed methods case study design, focusing on a single urban area and a specific cohort of pre-teen to teenage girls. The ability to generalise findings from this case study to other persons (e.g. different ethnicities), contexts (e.g. urban), and age group (e.g. pre-teenage) will thus be limited. That said, this largely qualitative approach allows for an in-depth exploration of the lived experiences of participants within their unique socio-demographic and geographic context. Such person- and situation-specific richness is a strength.

6.2. Sample

Recruitment focused on schools selected based on specific criteria to maximise sample diversity. Despite this, certain demographic biases may still exist depending on which schools responded to our efforts. Additionally, while we aimed to capture a range of socio-demographic backgrounds, thereby incorporating intersectionality considerations (e.g. gender and ethnicity), the small sample size of 24 participants inherently limits the diversity of experiences present in the data.

Given the particular participant group, there is potential for social desirability bias whereby individuals could be influenced by normative pressure. We have incorporated various techniques to limit this, such as building rapport, incorporating follow-up questions alongside the structured survey, and using probe questions following open-ended questions.

Attrition is a common challenge in longitudinal studies. While we have incorporated numerous reciprocal elements to retain participants (e.g. maintaining contact between phases of data collection), a reduction in sample size is likely between waves. This smaller sample may limit insight on trends from quantitative questions and reduce the richness of qualitative data, as fewer voices could be represented in later stages of the study, potentially limiting the depth and continuity of the data collected.

6.3. Generalisability and transferability

Given the case study design and small sample size, the findings of this study may not be fully generalisable to broader populations of pre-teen and teenage girls. The specific environmental, social, and cultural factors of the selected urban setting mean that the experiences observed may differ from those in other contexts.

The study's insights could still be transferable to similar urban settings with comparable socio-demographic factors and environmental conditions. Moreover, the varied sample in this study is likely to provide valuable insights into what pre-teenage and teenage girls like and dislike about outdoor spaces, which could inform future research. The results, particularly regarding preferences and barriers, may offer foundational knowledge for understanding this demographic's relationship with outdoor spaces. Additionally, there are ongoing studies with similar aims, and validating our findings against theirs or pooling data could enhance our

understanding. This collaborative approach could help strengthen the evidence base and provide a broader context for the findings.

6.4. Validity considerations

We incorporate several approaches to address validity and credibility of our analyses (Creswell & Miller, 2000). First, we acknowledge our bias towards a constructivist framework and reciprocal research approach that we bring to this research. Second, we employ multiple methods to generate multiple forms of evidence from which to find common themes. Third, we expressly chose a life course lens to guide the longitudinal exploration of (dis)engagement with nature alongside the exploration of specific topics of interest which we applied to our data. As we did this, we continuously sought both confirming and disconfirming evidence. Finally, while the data could be interpreted differently, and we will not be checking back with the participants to ensure our interpretations did not distort their experience, we nevertheless throughout our iterative analysis employ an additional dimension of triangulation through discussion and consensus building among multiple researchers from differing disciplines. After the completion of each wave of data collection, we will reflect on these considerations. Section 7.4 provides details on how we implemented validity and reliability principles in Wave 1.

Guided by Creswell (2015) and Creswell and Miller (2000), we incorporate several approaches to address the validity and credibility of our analyses. First, we acknowledge our bias towards a constructivist framework and reciprocal research approach, recognising that all qualitative research is shaped by the positionality of the researchers. Rather than compromising validity, this explicit acknowledgment strengthens trustworthiness by making our interpretive lens transparent and allowing for reflexive engagement throughout the research process. As Creswell and Miller (2000) suggest, researcher reflexivity is a key validity strategy, as it ensures that we remain critically aware of our assumptions and the potential influence of our positionality on the findings.

To enhance rigour, we employ multiple methods to generate different forms of evidence, enabling methodological triangulation to identify consistent themes and reduce potential biases. This aligns with Creswell and Miller's (2000) recommendation of triangulation as a strategy to increase credibility by cross-verifying data from different sources. In addition, we expressly chose a life course lens to guide the longitudinal exploration of (dis)engagement with nature, allowing us to track patterns of change over the course of the study and analyse shifts in participants' experiences. This approach ensures that findings are not based on a single moment in time but are instead contextualised within participants' broader developmental trajectories.

By following the same group of participants over multiple years, we can identify key moments that encourage or discourage their engagement with outdoor spaces. To enhance confirmability, we continuously seek both confirming and disconfirming evidence, a process that strengthens validity by preventing selective interpretation of data and ensuring our conclusions are based on a balanced and comprehensive analysis rather than assumptions. Additionally, we plan to incorporate participant validation (member checking) in later stages of the study, allowing participants to review and respond to interpretations of their narratives—an approach Creswell and Miller (2000) highlight as key to ensuring the credibility of qualitative findings.

After the completion of each wave of data collection, we will reflect on these considerations. While the data may allow for multiple interpretations, we do not check back with participants after each Wave of data collection to verify our interpretations. This decision is intentional, as we

aim to avoid influencing participants' own perceptions and experiences of the outdoors throughout the study. Maintaining this approach ensures that their engagement with outdoor spaces continues to develop naturally, without being shaped by prior discussions or researcher feedback. However, we will conduct participant checking after all three Waves of data collection are completed. Once findings have been analysed and interpreted, we will return to participants who remain engaged in the study to share summaries of their contributions and ask for feedback. This process ensures that they agree with how their experiences have been represented and provides an opportunity for them to clarify or expand on key points.

While we aim to include all participants in this process, we recognise that some may withdraw from the study before its completion. When participants drop out, we will reach out to ask whether they wish to continue receiving study updates and remain informed about key findings. Unless they request otherwise, we will retain the data they have contributed, as well as their contact details, as outlined in the consent form. If they do not respond, we will not contact them further with updates or participant checking. However, if they indicate a willingness to stay informed, they will still have the opportunity to engage in the checking process, even if they do not participate in Waves 2 or 3.

This participant-engaged validation enhances the validity of our research by ensuring that findings accurately reflect participants' lived experiences while minimising the likelihood of researcher-imposed interpretations in final publications.

In addition, we strengthen the reliability of our interpretations through a structured process of discussion and consensus-building amongst researchers from different disciplines. This means that, rather than relying on a single researcher's viewpoint, we bring together a team with expertise in areas such as environmental science, social science, psychology, and education, each offering unique perspectives on the data. These researchers meet regularly to review interview transcripts, visual timelines, and participant photographs, identifying recurring themes and potential contradictions.

During these discussions, we apply a process of peer debriefing, another strategy emphasised by Creswell and Miller (2000) to improve qualitative validity. This involves critically questioning one another's interpretations—for example, if one researcher sees a strong theme of safety concerns in outdoor spaces, another may challenge this by pointing to data that contradicts this perspective. Through this process, we examine whether our conclusions truly emerge from the data or are being shaped by our own disciplinary biases.

Additionally, we actively look for both confirming and disconfirming evidence, as suggested by Creswell and Miller (2000), ensuring that we do not only focus on findings that align with our expectations. If different researchers interpret a participant's experience in different ways, we deliberately explore these differences, asking what might explain them and whether additional context from the data can help resolve uncertainties. By engaging in this iterative process of discussion and critical reflection, we reduce the risk of individual bias and enhance the reliability of our findings.

7. Wave 1

Wave 1 of the Girls Outdoors Study aimed to establish a baseline for understanding how pre-teen girls engage with outdoor spaces as they transition from primary to secondary school. The primary objective was to explore their outdoor experiences, perceptions of nature, and the

factors influencing their (dis)engagement with the outdoors. By adopting a life course perspective, Wave 1 sought to capture how key life events - such as changing schools, forming new friendships, or moving to a new area - shaped their relationship with the outdoors, from early childhood to their current age (P7). This approach allowed for a deeper understanding of the complex social, environmental, and developmental factors driving changes in their outdoor activities, preferences, attitudes towards nature, and the ways they interact with different types of outdoor spaces, providing a foundation for subsequent waves of data collection and analysis.

7.1. Sample

The sample consists of 24 participants, including two sets of twins, all girls in Primary 7 (P7) from a large urban area, aged 10/11-12 years. A maximum of six girls were recruited from any one school, with participants recruited from schools across different catchment areas throughout the urban area. This approach ensured that the sample reflects diverse access to outdoor spaces in their local environments to capture a range of experiences related to outdoor engagement.

Demographic information for the sample was collected from 22 households, as only one parent/ carer per household completed the survey. Parents/ carers were given the option to leave questions unanswered, which accounts for variations in the totals for the below demographic categories.

The sample shows some range of ethnic backgrounds, with 77% of households (17) identifying as White Scottish, 9% (2) as Other White, and 5% (1) as Other African (Figure 1). In terms of religion, an equal proportion of households, 45% (10), identified as Christian or reported having no religious affiliation. Parental/ carer education levels varied. A large proportion, 41% (9), held higher degrees or professional qualifications, while 5% (1) reported having no formal qualifications. Equal numbers of parents/ carers, 14% (3), had a bachelor's degree, vocational or college qualifications, or secondary education (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Education across households (Wave 1)

Income levels across households also displayed variation. Twenty-three percent (5) of households reported earnings over £80,000 with another 18% (4) indicating earnings within the £70,001 to £80,000 range. Smaller proportions were distributed across lower income brackets, including 9% (2) in the £50,001 to £60,000 and £40,001 to £45,000 ranges, and 9% (2) in the

£20,001 to £25,000 range. A few households (1 each) reported incomes under £15,000 or between £15,001 and £20,000 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Income levels across households (Wave 1)

In terms of the total number of children per household, 23% (5 households) had 1 child, 50% (11 households) had 2 children, 18% (4 households) had 3 children, and 5% (1 household) had 4 children. The family composition in the sample shows that 50% (11 households) had 1 child under the age of 13, 36% (8 households) had 2 children, and 9% (2 households) had 3 children. For children aged 13 to 18, 36% (8 households) had 1 child, 5% (1 household) had 2 children, 18% (4 households) had 3 children, and 5% (1 household) had 4 children (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Total number of children per household (Wave 1)

7.2. Data collection methods

This section outlines the two key data collection methods used in Wave 1 of the Girls Outdoors Study: the structured interview (survey) and the semi-structured interview ("River of Life" method). These were audio-recorded and conducted in a single session with the participant.

7.2.1. Pilot

To assess the appropriateness and effectiveness of the interview components, a pilot study was conducted in September 2023 with a child from the target age group. The pilot aimed to test the suitability of the interview structure, question phrasing, and length, ensuring they were age-appropriate and capable of eliciting meaningful responses to inform the study objectives.

The pilot interviews were conducted by two members of the research team and were designed to allow participant to respond at their own pace to mirror the intended approach. No audio or visual recordings were made; instead, detailed notes were taken to capture the participant's reactions and suggestions for improvement. These notes were used to refine the interview process and were securely stored until the end of November 2023, after which they were destroyed. The privacy and confidentiality of the participant was strictly safeguarded. No data from the pilot study were or will be used in any research outputs. The insights gained from this pilot were invaluable in adjusting the structured and semi-structured interview ('River of Life' method) components to better suit the target age group for the main study.

7.2.2. Structured interview (survey)

The aim of the structured interview (survey; Appendix 1) was to capture an overview of topics related to engagement with the outdoors. The survey was developed with input from the project's Steering Group, incorporating recommendations to include quantitative scales assessing 'nature connectedness' and engagement with and access to outdoor spaces. These scales were based on measures developed by Natural England (PANS data; Natural England, 2020), NatureScot, and the University of Derby's Nature Connection Index (Richardson et al., 2019). Additionally, a set of items being developed to assess nature engagement capabilities (Irvine et al., in preparation) was included. The nature engagement capabilities scale statements were modified to simplify language in order to make them more understandable for and relevant to the age group.

The structured interview (survey), conducted at the start of the session and accompanied by follow-up questions, was used in place of a self-completion questionnaire to enhance both data quality and engagement. This method provided a more comprehensive snapshot of participants' outdoor space use and level of engagement with the outdoors before transitioning to the more detailed semi-structured interview ('River of Life' method).

7.2.3. Semi-structured interview ('River of Life' method)

The semi-structured interview ('River of Life' method), based on an interview guide adapted from Colley, Currie, et al. (2022), provided an in-depth exploration of the girls' outdoor experiences, spanning from their early childhood to the present. This approach allowed for a deeper understanding of how their engagement with outdoor spaces has evolved across the study.

Over the course of the data collection phase between November 2023 and March 2024, we refined the interview guide (Appendix 2) to focus on the most meaningful outdoor activities and preferences for outdoor spaces, shifting the emphasis from covering numerous individual experiences to capturing deeper, quality insights. This adjustment allowed for a more in-depth exploration of participants' likes, dislikes, and specific outdoor space preferences, providing richer insights into their engagement with outdoor spaces.

A key element of the semi-structured interview was the use of the adapted "River of Life" timeline; a visual tool with a theoretical foundation based on Colley, Currie, et al. (2022). This timeline helped map participants' key life events, regular outdoor activities, and one-off outdoor events,

providing a structure for the interview and a point of reference for future waves of data collection. Researchers handled the practical construction of this timeline during the interview to ensure participants remained focused and engaged in the co-creation process without distraction. This timeline not only facilitated meaningful engagement during the interview but will also serve as a memory for participants, providing them with a reflection of their journey at the study's conclusion.

7.3. Data analysis

The data analysis process for Wave 1 involves integrating the structured interviews, semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method), and visual timelines. Interview audio-recordings were transcribed and imported into NVivo (a tool to support qualitative analysis). The visual timelines were also imported into NVivo to be used in conjunction with the transcriptions, providing a reference point for the participants' narratives and adding a visual dimension to the analysis.

We are employing Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) to identify key themes aligned with the research questions for Wave 1. These themes focus on how to improve outdoor spaces for this demographic by examining participants' likes, dislikes, and preferences regarding outdoor spaces, as well as the factors influencing their engagement with the outdoors. Specifically, it aims to identify what is already available, what is lacking, and what changes are required to ensure that pre-teen girls feel safe, have better access, and are encouraged to spend more time in outdoor spaces (enablers). Additionally, it seeks to reveal the barriers preventing them from engaging (more) with the outdoors. Through this analytical framework, we aim to generate insights into how outdoor spaces can be more effectively tailored to meet the needs of P7 girls and to explore strategies for encouraging them to spend more (meaningful) time outdoors.

7.4. Validity and reliability

We implemented a structured and consistent approach throughout recruitment, data collection, and analysis. Despite extensive efforts to engage with schools on our priority list to get a diverse sample (see Section 4), we encountered limited response from some, which meant we had to contact schools that were not on our priority list, along with guide clubs. As a result, the final sample included fewer participants from lower-income backgrounds and underrepresented communities than initially intended. This limitation, along with its potential implications, is further discussed in Section 7.5.

Throughout the recruitment process, every participant received the same project information and experience at the James Hutton Institute and engaged with identical interview materials. The participants were of the same age group, which further supported consistency in the data collection process. Detailed notes and debriefs were maintained during and after each interview to document any adjustments or modifications made throughout the process.

We embrace the reflexive nature of RTA, meaning we continuously reflected on how our values, experiences, and potential biases might influence data collection and interpretation. This reflexivity remains integral throughout the analysis to ensure a nuanced and unbiased understanding of the findings.

We will ensure that thematic saturation will be reached, where no new themes emerge during coding, confirming that all relevant aspects of the data have been captured. Additionally, we will

strengthen validity by triangulating our findings with other data sources, thereby gaining a fuller understanding of the phenomenon under study.

To reinforce reliability, we will keep detailed records of our coding and theme development (audit trails) and involve multiple researchers in the analysis. This collaborative approach will facilitate the comparison of interpretations, promoting both transparency and coherence in the analysis. It will also ensure that the identified themes are not only consistent with the data but are closely aligned with the interpretive framework of the research.

7.5. Limitations and strengths

This section outlines the limitations of the research process of Wave 1, which may have impacted the data collection and interpretation process. First, both teachers and parents/ carers had some influence prior to the interviews, potentially shaping the participants' expectations and responses. Input from these adults may have primed the girls in certain ways, particularly if they were encouraged to participate or had pre-existing attitudes toward outdoor activities.

Despite our dedicated efforts to ensure diversity in the sample, practical constraints shaped the final participant group. We initially aimed for diverse representation across socio-economic and ethnic backgrounds, actively reaching out to specific schools. However, responses from schools varied widely, with some schools unable or unwilling to engage due to scheduling demands, limited capacity, or lack of familiarity with the project. Our existing professional connections with certain schools facilitated some recruitment, though this also limited outreach beyond these networks. Additionally, parental/ carer factors such as availability, understanding of the project, and willingness to participate further influenced the composition of our sample.

These recruitment challenges may have introduced a selection bias, potentially skewing the sample towards families with pre-existing interest or comfort in outdoor activities. This pattern is not uncommon in research, especially when working with certain demographics where distrust, unfamiliarity with research processes, or shame factors can impact recruitment (Houghton et al., 2020). Our experience underscores the complexity of recruiting a truly representative sample and the importance of acknowledging these limitations in interpreting study outcomes.

Although efforts were made to mitigate bias by creating a more appealing research experience (see Section 2.3), the nature of the study's topic may have still influenced participants' engagement and perspectives in ways that were not entirely controllable. That said, initial insight suggests that the sample captured a reasonable level of diversity in this regard, as some participants came from non-outdoorsy backgrounds and reported limited engagement in outdoor activities.

In addition, the research process itself may influence how participants view and engage with nature in the future. Reflecting on their outdoor activities as part of the study might serve as a motivator for spending more time outdoors, potentially reinforced by parents/ carers encouraging them to be outside more. Conversely, some participants may develop a negative view of outdoor activities as a result of their involvement in the study, potentially leading to aversion rather than increased engagement. These varying impacts highlight the complexity of studying perceptions and behaviours in real-world contexts, where participants' experiences may be shaped by the research process itself.

The presence of varying numbers of researchers (mostly 2, occasionally 3) may have introduced some inconsistencies in the data collection process. Although the study protocol was followed,

differences in researchers' interaction styles, as well as the varying number of researchers in each session, could have influenced the interview dynamics and potentially affected the participants' responses.

Lastly, the presence of family members, during the interviews, including one parent/ carer who was always present, as well as siblings who occasionally attended due to childcare issues, may have influenced the interview dynamics. The presence of a parent/ carer (and sibling) could have affected the participants' comfort levels, which potentially constrained their openness or changed the way they expressed their thoughts and opinions. This may have impacted the quality and/or depth of the data collected.

These limitations highlight the challenges of conducting research with young participants and emphasise the need for caution in generalising the findings beyond the sample.

7.6. Lessons learnt

Several key lessons emerged from the research process in Wave 1, particularly around recruitment and engagement with schools and young participants. A significant insight was the reality check in the complexities of working with schools. Flexibility and adaptability were crucial at every stage, from initial recruitment to conducting interviews, and it quickly became apparent that to work effectively with young people, researchers must be prepared to pivot based on logistical constraints. This meant we had to adjust our recruitment expectations and work with schools that were willing and able to participate. In addition, variations in the number of researchers present, the occasional presence of siblings, and different family dynamics highlighted the need for adaptability during the interviews, tailoring each session to the specific circumstances to ensure comfort and openness. This flexibility was key to managing diverse situations while still gathering valuable data.

Parental/ carer involvement also emerged as essential during interviews. Having a parent/ carer present proved invaluable in building trust and establishing rapport, particularly with 10-/11- and 12-year-old girls who often found it challenging to discuss personal details or recall specific memories. Parents helped to create a supportive environment, enabling participants to feel more at ease and enriching the data by providing context and additional insights.

Finally, one of the most positive outcomes was the enthusiastic response from participants themselves. Many of the girls – and often also their parents/ carers - expressed genuine enjoyment and excitement about their involvement in the study, often mentioning that they found the experience engaging and fun. This positive feedback from participants not only reinforced the value of our approach but also emphasised the importance of creating an enjoyable and memorable research experience for younger participants, which can help foster positive associations with research and improve engagement in longitudinal studies.

8. Wave 2

We will continue to explore how pre-teen/teen girls (11-12 (13) years old during Wave 2 data collection) engage with outdoor spaces, building on the data collected in Wave 1. The methods for this phase will include semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method) and photovoice technique, both designed to capture participants' evolving relationship with outdoor environments. This phase specifically focuses on how the transition from primary to secondary school has impacted participants' engagement with the outdoors, along with their perceptions of

‘quality’ in outdoor spaces. This section outlines the key components of the research process for Wave 2, including details on the sample, ethical considerations, data collection methods, and analysis. Additionally, it addresses potential limitations, including validity and reliability, specific to this phase of the study.

8.1. Sample

As this is a longitudinal study, the sample for Wave 2 will consist of the same cohort of participants from Wave 1, originally composed of 24 teenage girls from a large urban area. Due to the retention activities implemented between Wave 1 and Wave 2, we anticipate a low attrition rate, expecting between 15 and 20 girls to participate in Wave 2, which is scheduled for Spring 2025 (April-June).

8.2. Ethical considerations

Informed consent is a critical element of this phase. Both participants and their parents/ carers will be thoroughly briefed on the study’s goals, methods, and any potential risks, ensuring they understand what participation in Wave 2 entails. This informed consent process includes explicit discussion of topics that could arise during interviews, such as disclosure of sensitive or potentially distressing information. Participants will be reminded that they should avoid discussing illegal activities, self-harm, or harm to others. While these topics were mentioned as potential areas of concern in Wave 1, they did not emerge in interviews; however, given participants’ age and the changes they are experiencing due to their transition from primary to secondary school, there is a possibility that such issues might arise now.

To address this, we will emphasise the importance of discussing boundaries and confidentiality during the consent process. Participants will be encouraged to share only what they are comfortable disclosing and to notify a researcher if any topic makes them feel uncomfortable. The research team is also trained to handle disclosures sensitively and appropriately, with protocols in place for responding to any indication of harm to the participant or others. This approach aims to protect participant safety while fostering a trusting environment in which participants feel secure in expressing themselves within the study's ethical framework.

In addition, the photovoice technique presents specific ethical considerations. As described in prior studies, such as Langhout (2014), participants will be instructed to avoid taking photographs of individuals without their consent and to refrain from capturing images that could be considered unsafe or inappropriate. Since participants will be asked to reflect on personal experiences in both interviews and through their photographs, emotional wellbeing will be monitored throughout, with access to support services provided if needed.

8.3. Data collection methods

This section outlines the methods that will be used to gather data from participants in Wave 2 of the study. The methods include semi-structured interviews (‘River of Life’ method) and the photovoice technique, both of which are designed to elicit rich, qualitative data about the girls' perceptions and use of outdoor spaces. The semi-structured interviews (‘River of Life’ method) allow for in-depth discussions about changes in participants' lives and their use of outdoor spaces since Wave 1, while the photovoice technique engages participants in visual storytelling, offering in-depth insights into their experiences. Together, these methods aim to capture a comprehensive understanding of the participants' evolving relationships with outdoor spaces, providing valuable data for analysis.

8.3.1. Part 1: Semi-structured interview – River of Life

The semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method) will consist of open-ended questions designed to explore changes in the participants' lives since Wave 1, continuing the timeline established in the first wave of data collection using the adapted 'River of Life' method. This method involves participants mapping out significant events or changes in their lives, allowing for a visual and narrative continuation of their personal experiences across the study. In Wave 2, the interview questions will explore recurring and one-off outdoor experiences, focusing on how their engagement with outdoor spaces has evolved over the past year. The interviews will investigate any significant life events that may have influenced these changes, such as transitioning to secondary school, forming new friendships, or relocating to a new area. The semi-structured interview format allows for flexibility, enabling the researchers to probe deeper into specific areas while maintaining a conversational flow. At the start of the interview, we will provide a brief summary of key points from their previous responses in Wave 1 to help them reflect on any changes since then. From there, we will ask open-ended questions to encourage discussion. Some guiding questions will include:

- How are you using outdoor spaces now compared to last year?
- What has triggered these changes in how you use different types of outdoor spaces?
- What do you like or dislike about the outdoor spaces you visit?

These questions, particularly those addressing likes and dislikes, transition into the photovoice technique. By first discussing their outdoor engagement through conversation and with the help of the visual timeline, participants are encouraged to reflect on their engagement with the outdoors. This reflection then helps guide us to the photovoice part of the interview. The photovoice technique will have participants visually document their experiences and preferences related to outdoor environments to further explore their perceptions of outdoor spaces, as further described in the following section.

8.3.2. Part 2: Photo-elicited interview

The photovoice technique is a participatory research method that allows participants to document their experiences through photography and then use these images as a basis for discussion in interviews. This method has been successfully employed in studies involving youth and marginalised groups, enabling participants to express complex thoughts and feelings through visual media (Ward et al., 2023; Carpenter, 2022; Langhout, 2014).

The photovoice technique in Wave 2 is specifically aimed at exploring participants' perceptions of 'outdoor space quality' by having them visually capture their experiences in outdoor spaces. This approach will help to uncover how the girls define and experience quality in outdoor spaces, specifically in urban outdoor spaces. These visual and narrative insights will provide a deeper understanding of how teenage girls engage with outdoor spaces and what aspects they value or wish to improve.

Photography Assignment and Prompts

In June 2024, we invited participants to consider taking photographs during their time outdoors as a way to visually document their experiences in nature. Participation in the photography activity is entirely optional, and all participants are encouraged to join Wave 2 regardless of

whether they choose to take photos. Our aim is to provide a flexible and supportive experience, adapting to each participant's comfort levels and preferences.

The initial instructions were intentionally broad, giving participants the freedom to capture any outdoor experiences that resonate with them. To further support this activity, we plan to follow up closer to the interviews in spring 2025 with additional guidance, offering prompts to help participants focus on themes central to the study, such as what they enjoy or find challenging in outdoor spaces, and their ideas for improving these environments. This will be guided by prompts such as:

- Take a photo of an outdoor space you enjoy spending time in. What do you like about it?
- Take a photo of an outdoor space you don't enjoy or avoid. What do you dislike about it?
- Take a photo of something in an outdoor space that you think could be made better.
- Take a photo of specific things in an outdoor space that are important to you.

Participants will also be encouraged to write captions for each photo, explaining the meaning behind their chosen images. These captions will serve as the starting point for discussion during the interview, allowing for a deeper exploration of the participant's experiences and thoughts on 'outdoor space quality'.

Photo-Elicited Interview Process

For the photo-elicited interview, participants will be invited to select up to 10 photos for in-depth discussion. In addition, we will present a carefully selected set of images specifically prepared for the interview, informed by findings from Wave 1. These images will showcase a variety of outdoor spaces, including close-up photos that highlight specific features of these environments. Participants will be encouraged to reflect on what they like and dislike about each depicted space or particular aspect of the environment, as well as to suggest potential improvements. We will use a modified version of the SHOWD technique to guide the discussion. The traditional SHOWD framework (Langhout, 2014) will be adapted in the following ways:

- **See:** What do you see in this photo?
- **Happening:** What is happening in this outdoor space that you like / dislike?
- **Our:** How does this outdoor space relate to your life and routine?
- **Why:** Why do you think you enjoy / dislike this outdoor space?
- **Do:** What can be done to improve this outdoor space?

During the interview, we will also explore visual semiotics, where relevant. For example, a locked gate might be interpreted as representing exclusion, while an open outdoor space (i.e. an area that is accessible, unrestricted, and welcoming to the public) could symbolise freedom or a sense of comfort.

8.4. Data analysis

We will continue using Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA), as previously applied in Wave 1. This approach emphasises the researcher's active role in identifying and interpreting themes from the data. RTA is flexible and allows themes to emerge naturally without strictly predefined themes to encourage continuous reflection and re-evaluation. Based on Wave 1 and prior theory of outdoor space quality and perceptions, key themes we anticipate include:

- Accessibility and inclusivity of outdoor spaces.
- Perceived safety in outdoor spaces.
- Aesthetic and environmental value of outdoor spaces.
- The social function of outdoor spaces (meeting friends, relaxation, etc.).
- Suggested improvements (e.g. more facilities).

The research team will examine the photographs and accompanying narratives to identify themes, patterns, and insights using a structured approach. The analysis will begin with a descriptive phase, focusing on the visual elements of the photographs, such as composition, colours, and subjects. This phase includes documenting what the photos depict, such as specific outdoor environments (e.g. parks, beaches, woodlands) and potential physical barriers like fences or unsafe conditions.

Next, a thematic analysis will be conducted to code and categorise the content of both the visual and narrative data. This process aims to uncover recurring themes, such as perceptions of safety, aesthetic appeal, or accessibility of outdoor spaces, and to identify patterns that align with the study's research objectives. Visual semiotics are analysed to interpret the symbols and cultural messages conveyed within the photos. These interpretations will be cross-referenced with the interview transcripts to provide contextual insights. These layers of analysis will enhance the richness of the findings, offering nuanced insights into participants' evolving engagement with and perceptions of outdoor spaces.

Through this analytical framework, we aim to generate valuable insights into how outdoor spaces can be better designed to meet the needs of S1 girls. Additionally, we will explore strategies to encourage them to spend more (meaningful) time outdoors and contribute to Work Package 1 by examining the quality of outdoor spaces for this demographic.

Methods Triangulation:

To enhance the validity of the study, multiple data collection methods are employed, ensuring that findings are not reliant on a single source. Wave 2 integrates:

- **Semi-structured interviews**, using an **adapted 'River of Life' method** to track changes in outdoor engagement since Wave 1.
- **Photovoice technique**, allowing participants to visually document and discuss their experiences of greenspaces.

Since participants were invited to take photos in June 2024, there is some uncertainty regarding the extent to which they engaged with this task—whether they took photos consistently, sporadically, or at all. Additionally, participants may find it difficult to retrieve images taken many months ago. To address this potential limitation and ensure meaningful discussions, we will also provide a carefully selected set of photographs representing a variety of outdoor spaces and features. We will keep track of which participants bring their own photos. Photographs will be used as prompts for reflection and discussion, allowing all participants, including those who did not take photos themselves, to contribute insights on green/blue space quality and engagement. Further details on this process are outlined in the 'Photo-Elicited Interview Process' section below (Section 8).

This approach ensures that the photovoice component remains a valuable method of exploration, even if participants bring a limited number of personal photographs or none at all. By incorporating both participant-generated and researcher-provided images, we maintain methodological triangulation and create a balanced framework for understanding how S1 girls perceive and experience outdoor spaces.

By cross-referencing themes emerging from interviews, visual timelines, and participant-generated photos, methodological triangulation strengthens the robustness of the findings and reduces the risk of bias or misinterpretation.

8.5. Limitations and strengths

Wave 2 faces several potential limitations. One concern is participant attrition; despite our retention efforts, there is a possibility of losing participants, which could reduce the sample size.

The participatory and subjective nature of the photovoice technique presents inherent challenges to traditional concepts of validity and reliability. However, previous studies have shown that triangulation can enhance validity in photovoice research. For instance, Oviedo et al. (2022) combined surveys with photography and park audits to cross-validate findings, while Heidelberger and Smith (2016) employed both quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure that photographic findings were supported by interview data. In this study, we will use methods triangulation, combining photovoice with in-depth interviews, to enhance the validity of our findings. This triangulation will allow for a richer dataset and cross-verification between participants' visual and verbal expressions of their outdoor experiences.

To address reliability, the coding process in our thematic analysis will involve independent verification by multiple researchers. This approach aims to minimise potential biases, ensuring that the analysis remains as rigorous as possible.

9. Wave 3

Wave 3 will build on the foundations established in Waves 1 and 2, with an expanded focus on participants' nature engagement capabilities and respectful behaviour in outdoor spaces ('care for nature'). In addition to the structured and semi-structured interviews used in Wave 1, Wave 3 will introduce the use of a Virtual Tour of Nature (VTN) as a tool to capture insights that may not be fully accessible through interviews alone. This approach leverages the work conducted in Work Package 3 of the *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* project (JHI-C6-1), which developed VTNs to explore whether virtual experiences can encourage nature engagement amongst individuals who are less confident or infrequent visitors to outdoor spaces, such as the demographic of the GO study. This mixed method approach in Wave 3 will allow for a deeper exploration of participants' perceptions of and behaviour in familiar and unfamiliar outdoor spaces.

9.1. Sample

As a longitudinal study, the sample for Wave 3 will consist of the same cohort of participants from Waves 1 and 2, initially comprising 24 pre-teenage girls (aged 10/11-12) from a large urban area, who are now in Secondary 2. Since data collection occurs at the end of the school term, the majority of participants will be 13-14 years old. Due to the retention activities implemented between Waves 1 and 2, and again between Waves 2 and 3, we anticipate a low attrition rate. We expect at least 10 - 15 girls to participate in Wave 3, scheduled for Spring 2026 (April-June).

9.2. Data collection methods

Wave 3 will build on previous methods, combining structured interviews, semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method), and a new visual method – VTN – to explore participants' evolving relationships with outdoor spaces. The structured interview (Section 5.2.1), replicated

from Wave 1, will enable direct comparison between pre-teen and teenage years, offering insights into participants' outdoor habits, capabilities, and connection to nature across the study. The semi-structured interview ('River of Life' method) (Section 5.2.2) will use open-ended questions to explore changes in outdoor engagement since Wave 2, extending the timeline established in previous waves.

Finally, the VTN component (Section 5.2.3) will provide participants with an opportunity to engage with a range of outdoor settings. This will allow them to reflect on and discuss their capabilities, confidence, and understanding of how to care for and respect nature across different environments. The following sections provide further detail on each of these methods.

9.2.1. Part 1: Structured interviews (survey)

In Wave 3, we will replicate the structured interview (survey) process used in Wave 1 to enable direct comparison between pre-teen and teenage years. Developed with input from the project's Steering Group, this interview (survey) incorporates scales in relation to participants' frequency of visits to different types of outdoor spaces, their relationship with and connection to nature, and nature engagement capabilities as well as respect to nature.

At the start of the session, we will ask participants to respond to the structured interview (survey) questions, followed by additional probing questions to provide a comprehensive snapshot of their recent outdoor habits and use of different types of outdoor spaces. The focus will be on the three months preceding the interview, meaning that depending on when the interview takes place between April and June, participants will be asked about their use of outdoor spaces between January and May 2026.

9.2.2. Part 2: Semi-structured interviews – River of Life

The semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method) for Wave 3 will consist of open-ended questions designed to explore the participants' experiences and changes in their lives and outdoor (dis)engagement since Wave 2, continuing the timeline established in Waves 1 and 2 using the adapted 'River of Life' method. This method enables participants to visually map out significant life events and changes, offering a narrative and visual continuation of their personal experiences across the study. In Wave 3, the interview will focus on shifts in their use of outdoor spaces during the past year and any notable life events that may have influenced these changes.

The semi-structured format provides flexibility, allowing researchers to delve deeper into specific areas of interest while maintaining a natural flow. Some guiding questions will include:

- How are you using outdoor spaces now compared to last year?
- What has triggered these changes in how you use outdoor spaces?
- What do you like or dislike about the outdoor spaces you visit?

These questions, particularly those addressing preferences and dislikes, will transition into the second part of the interview, which incorporates a VTN to explore participants' relationships with outdoor spaces and their nature engagement capabilities.

9.2.3. Part 3: Virtual Tour of Nature

Participants will experience a VTN, developed by the Work Package 3 team, featuring a range of outdoor environments such as an urban beach, river walk, park, and wooded area. The post-tour interview will delve deeper into participants' comfort levels when exploring these various outdoor

settings and their understanding of respectful engagement with nature. The VTN-based interview builds on themes introduced in the structured interviews conducted in Wave 1 and revisited at the start of Wave 3. Insights from analysis of the Wave 1 structured interviews will inform the design of the VTN interview guide, ensuring relevance and continuity. During the structured interviews in Wave 3, detailed notes will be taken to further refine and tailor the VTN interview questions, aligning them closely with participants' responses, particularly those related to the nature engagement capability and connection to nature set of questions of the structured interview. The VTN provides an interactive layer to assess participants' confidence and awareness in different outdoor spaces. This will allow for insights into how the participants' relationship with outdoor spaces and their attitudes towards care for nature have evolved from their pre-teen years (P7) to their teenage years (S2). These shifts will be considered alongside any relevant changes identified during Wave 2.

During the VTN, participants will be asked to follow a think-aloud protocol, sharing their thoughts and impressions as they engage with the VTN. Afterwards, we will ask further questions about their experience with the VTN, exploring whether it would motivate them to spend more time outdoors and encourage them to explore outdoor spaces independently, without being accompanied by parents/ carers. In Wave 1, many participants expressed discomfort in visiting outdoor spaces other than urban parks without their parents/ carers, a sentiment that may have shifted as they have grown older. We will also further investigate what 'care for nature' means to them and how they would prepare for exploring outdoor spaces respectfully.

In addition to assessing their comfort, confidence, and respect for nature, we will explore additional factors that could enhance their sense of preparedness and safety when navigating both familiar and unfamiliar outdoor spaces. This includes examining whether they feel guidance on 'outdoor behaviour' could be more effectively integrated into a VTN to provide an informative and supportive resource on respectful nature engagement. Insights from this exploration could help refine the VTN as a tool for better guidance and confidence-building in outdoor settings.

9.3. Data analysis

The data analysis for Wave 3 will follow the same approach used in previous waves, employing Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) to identify key themes from the structured and semi-structured interviews ('River of Life' method), along with the VTN. Audio recordings from the interviews will be transcribed and uploaded to NVivo for coding and analysis, allowing for the integration of data across the structured / semi-structured interviews, timelines, and discussion around the VTN. By combining qualitative insights from the interviews with the reflections gathered from the VTN, we will explore patterns of change in nature engagement and capabilities, and care for nature across the study (e.g. between Wave 1 & Wave 3 using structured interview data), with a particular focus on identifying shifts between pre-teen and teenage years. Themes will be developed iteratively, guided by the research questions and participants' outdoor habits, preferences, capabilities, and understanding of respectful nature engagement.

9.4. Limitations and strengths

The introduction of the VTN presents both opportunities and challenges. While it offers valuable insights into nature engagement capabilities, it may not fully capture participants' real-world experiences in outdoor spaces. The "snapshot" nature that was captured in the VTN by the WP3 team shows a specific moment in time and may not reflect seasonal changes or other environmental variations that could influence how participants experience, interact with, or care

for outdoor spaces in reality. In addition, participants may have varying levels of familiarity and comfort with technology like a VTN, which could affect their ability to engage fully, with technical issues such as glitches, lag, or discomfort potentially further disrupting the interview flow. However, the use of mediated nature through the VTN offers a unique strength, as it enables participants to explore and engage with diverse types of outdoor settings that they might not otherwise have access to, broadening the scope of their nature engagement and enriching the insights from the 'River of Life' interview.

Lastly, while efforts will be made to minimise attrition, the longitudinal nature of the study may still result in further reduction in the sample size, which could impact the richness and continuity of the data collected across the three waves.

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